

University of Ioannina
School of Engineering

Department of Materials Science & Engineering

Composite & Smart Materials Lab

(<http://csmlab.materials.uoi.gr>)

MONITORING THE PROPERTIES OF CEMENTITIOUS COMPOSITE MATERIALS WITH ADVANCED FUNCTIONALITIES

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✓ Green Buildings

✓ Energy Harvesting

✓ Functional Cement

THERMOELECTRIC MICRO- / NANO- CEMENTITIOUS COMPOSITES FOR POTENTIAL THERMAL ENERGY HARVESTING

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Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) & Carbon Fibers (CFs) as fillers are used:

- to improve mechanical properties
- to impart functionalities
 - electrical & thermoelectrical properties

L: distance between the electrodes, A: electrode area inside the cement

Key Challenges:

- Avoid agglomeration and achieve homogenous dispersion

Goal:

- Development of a reliable non-destructive methodology to:
 - ✓ Monitor and control the materials' quality
 - ✓ Detect the changes in the electrical properties during hydration
- Improve the Mechanical Properties
- Develop sensing abilities

An Introduction to Impedance Spectroscopy

$$|Z|(\omega) = Z'(\omega) - iZ''(\omega)$$

Experimental Protocol – Hydration Process

- Impedance measurements:**
- After Mixing
 - 1 day of Hydration
 - 28 days of Hydration

To detect the changes in the electrical properties

Frequency range (10^{-1} - $5 \cdot 10^6$ Hz)

MFIA- Impedance Analyzer

Embedded Titanium mesh electrodes

- From the measurements:**
- ✓ Impedance, $|Z|$
 - ✓ Real Resistance, Z'
 - ✓ Imaginary Reactance, Z''

* By cement weight

Experimental Protocol – Mechanical Testing/ Sensing

Mechanical Testing

Schematic representation of 3-Point bending test

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3FL}{2bd^2}$$

Schematic representation of Compressive test

$$\sigma_c = \frac{F}{A}$$

Piezoresistive sensing

Schematic representation of piezoresistive sensing

F: 2 → 8kN

$\Delta R/R_0\%$

Results - CNTs dispersion

At the frequency of 0.05Hz

Sample	Z (Ohm) _{30min}	Z (Ohm) _{60min}
0.1wt.%SWCNTs	2.94*10 ¹²	1.41*10 ⁵
0.5wt.%SWCNTs	1.63*10 ¹²	5.95*10 ⁴

- ✓ **0.1wt.%SWCNTs** A drop of |Z| by seven orders of magnitude, formation of a conductive network
- ✓ **0.5wt.%SWCNTs** A drop of |Z| by eight orders of magnitude, formation of a conductive network
- ✓ **0.5wt.% SWCNTs** Lowest values

Results – Electrical Properties After Mixing

Results – Electrical Properties 1st day of Hydration Process

Results – Electrical Properties 28th day of Hydration Process

- ↑ values of $|Z|$ for 0.1 wt. % CFs as the reference cement, no formation of a conductive network.
- ↓ values of $|Z|$ for 0.1wt. % SWCNTs in relation to reference cement & the 0.1 wt. % CFs, conductive network.
- ↓ values of $|Z|$ for 0.5wt.% SWCNTs 7 hybrid 0.1wt. %SWCNTs &0.5wt.% CFs

Results – Mechanical Properties

Results - Sensing

- Impedance Spectroscopy is a non - destructive technique that can evaluate the CNTs dispersion and the existence of a conductive network .
- 60min of sonication seems to be the optimum sonication time for all cases to avoid agglomeration and achieve homogenous dispersion with electrical properties.
- It is not feasible to form a conductive network for the composites with low concentration of CFs.
- The increase of CNTs/CFs concentration is resulting in lower $|Z|$ values compared to reference cement.
- The type of the reinforcement affects the electrical properties of the composites since the lowest values in the impedance $|Z|$ is presenting by the composite with 0.5wt.% SWCNTs &the hybrid composite with 0.1wt.%SWCNTs &0.5wt.% CFs, following by the composite with 0.5wt.% CFs and the composite with 0.1wt.%SWCNTs.
- The incorporation of the CNTs/CFs into the cement matrix improved the mechanical properties of the cement composites.
- The hybrid composite with 0.1wt.%SWCNTs & 0.5wt.% CFs presents the highest values in flexural strength while the nanocomposite with 0.1wt.%SWCNTs presents the highest values in compressive strength.
- The composites above the percolation threshold exhibit remarkable piezoresistive characteristics.

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Thank you!

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- **Hierarchical** composites & interfaces
- **Hybrid** composites
- **Simulation** & modeling
- **Self-healing** polymers & composites

- Non-Destructive Evaluation (**NDE**)
- On-line Structural Health Monitoring (**SHM**)
- **Mechanical / thermomechanical** characterization
- **Thermoelectric** composites & energy harvesting

